

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN IMPROVING THE HEALTH OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the main approaches to the use of sports games in the school physical education system. The most important goals of playing sports in a general education school are to introduce and teach students about the types of sports games and exercises, to lay the foundation of correct technique and to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills for sports competitions from a young age. to teach correctly when leaving.

This Law is new in accordance with the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports" dated September 4, 2015 LRU №-394 adopted in the revision¹ [1].

¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/-63106>

In recent times, it has been increasingly realized that the traditional and long-practiced forms of physical education and sports of the young generation no longer meet modern requirements, and it is necessary to transform them into more effective forms. Based on this, there is a need to search for new ideas and approaches to the organization of physical education and sports activities using innovative pedagogical technologies [2].

The most effective way to increase movement efficiency is physical activity. The content of physical education is represented by a complex of material, aesthetic and spiritual values. The result of physical training is the level of perfection of physical training and skills, abilities, high development of vital forces, sports achievements, moral, aesthetic, intellectual development, orientation to a healthy lifestyle.

Today, the main goals and tasks of physical education and sports activities in general education schools are to increase physical culture among young students, to form preparation for a healthy lifestyle, to develop interest in sports activities, to perform physical exercises regularly, to develop moral, emotional, is aimed at forming and developing intellectual, socio-cultural and aesthetic personality, creative abilities and cognitive needs [3].

The social importance of physical education should be understood as the following relationships and tasks: It is possible to briefly influence the connection of physical education with mental, aesthetic and labor education.

Mental education. Physical education serves in the development of mental education, depending on the content and direction of each field or

process. For example: in sports or when artists (ballet) figure skating on ice, knowing the directions and how many times to turn is the feeling of being mentally controlled.

Labor education. The social essence of physical education means increasing the ability to work. This includes production gymnastics, various exercises and games during breaks, sports training on the day off, trips and other direct services.

The role of physical education in the implementation of aesthetic education has its own characteristics. This is expressed in dances, ballet, circus, and games such as scarcity. In the art of singing, physical exercises are also widely used to deepen breathing and train the throat with fresh air. Artistic, rhythmic (aerobic) gymnastics, jumping on a trampoline, swimming, underwater gymnastics (synchronized swimming), ice skating and other fields are related to artistic and aesthetic aspects of physical education and sports.

When using physical education and sports for health purposes, the health-giving forces of nature (water, air, sun) and hygienic requirements are fully observed. For this reason, natural and special processes related to human activity are embodied in the socio-educational features of physical education and sports.

In the social-educational features of physical education and sports, health-improving activities are a social-pedagogical process of great importance. On this basis, the training of specialized personnel in the field of physical education and sports is considered an important process of state importance. This, in turn, is related to meeting the needs of physical education and sports activities, and further improving the socio-cultural conditions of

the population. In this way, the activities carried out by the President and the government of the Republic are bearing their high-level results. For this reason, the number of people engaged in one or another type of physical education and sports in all strata of the population is increasing. This is a sign of the essence of social and educational features of physical education and sports [4].

In the educational system, pedagogues often use four main directions of physical education and sports training. The first direction is aimed primarily at the acquisition of certain knowledge, as well as the development of skills and competencies of students in the field of physical education and sports. In the framework of the second direction, attention is mainly paid to the high level of development of physical qualities and training efficiency by increasing the number of mandatory training sessions. The third direction is focused on sports, and is primarily based on the rational combination of classroom and classroom forms of training, implementation of certain types of sports. The main task in this process is the formation of systematic training skills for preferred types of physical activity.

In the framework of the fourth direction, the health of students and the level of their physical development, physical fitness is considered the highest value of a person [5].

Full-fledged physical education work at school requires good equipment of the training place, purchase and preparation of necessary tools and

equipment. Therefore, the work plan envisages the purchase of sports equipment and equipment at the expense of the budget, and their preparation by the efforts of students, parents and guardians. The annual general plan of the school also reflects the promotion of physical education and sports. The school's general work plan for physical education and sports for the new academic year will be developed on the eve of the end of the academic year. During the summer vacation, preparations for the new academic year are carried out according to the developed plan of the school [6].

The family plays a big role in the upbringing of the child. So, the first thing a child should do in physical education is exercise in the morning. It is important to find out what kind of sport the student's soul is connected to and enroll him in a sports school and fitness center. It is very important to teach the child to have active rest: walking, exercising, walking in the park, playing on the children's playground.

Thus, the role of physical education in the comprehensive development of the student is undeniable. Parents should be active in order to teach physical education to the child with love, because they are the main example of the child [7].

Sports games effectively affect the psychological and pedagogical learning processes of schoolchildren: they develop abilities such as thinking, attention, memory, perception, imagination, reading, and physiologically improve the respiratory system, metabolism, blood circulation.

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